

Table 2. Information of SPPH in patients with/without antenatal PPH risk

		Without antenatal PPH risk (N=121)	With antenatal PPH risk (N=203)	P-value
Midwifery grade	Secondary midwifery hospital	64(74.4)	22(25.6)	<0.01
	Tertiary midwifery hospital	57(23.9)	181(76.1)	
Age(year)		32.4±4.5	34.6±4.3	<0.01
	<35	83(68.6)	84(41.4)	<0.01
	35-39	30(24.8)	68(33.5)	0.11
	≥40	8(6.6)	21(10.3)	0.32
Gestational weeks(w)		39.1±2.4	35.1±4.0	<0.01
Hight(cm)		162.0±5.1	162.3±4.6	0.78
Parity	0	91(75.2)	94(46.3)	<0.01
	1	27(22.3)	94(46.3)	<0.01
	≥2	3(2.5)	33(16.3)	<0.01
Delivery mode	Vaginal	66(54.5)	30(14.8)	<0.01
	Caesarean	55(45.5)	173(85.2)	
Etiology	Tone	74(61.2)	50(24.6)	<0.01
	Tissue	17(14.0)	134(66.0)	<0.01
	Trauma	21(17.4)	4(2.0)	<0.01
	Thrombin	9(7.4)	15(7.4)	>0.99
Results	Amount of bleeding (ml)	2281±1111	2397±1051	0.35
	< 2000	60(49.6)	88(43.3)	0.30
	2000-3999	50(41.3)	107(52.7)	0.05
	≥4000	11(9.1)	18(8.9)	>0.99
	Max	5700	7500	
	Amount of Bleeding in vaginal delivery ^a	2133±975	2433±839	0.15
	< 2000	31(47)	11(36.7)	0.38
	2000-3999	31(47)	16(53.3)	0.66
	≥4000	4(6.1)	2(6.7)	>0.99
	Amount of Bleeding in CS ^b	2460±1240	2391±1086	0.69
	< 2000	27(49.1)	77(44.5)	0.64
	2000-3999	19(34.5)	91(52.6)	0.02
	≥4000	9(16.4)	16(9.2)	0.14
	Admission to ICU	36(29.8)	113(55.7)	<0.01
	PPH complications	54(44.6)	35(17.2)	<0.01
Coagulation disorders	41(33.9)	24(11.8)	<0.01	
Shock (%)	28(23.1)	18(8.9)	<0.01	
Kidney damage	7(5.8)	9(4.4)	0.60	
Cardiopulmonary function disorders	5(4.1)	8(3.9)	>0.99	
Transfusion	Rbc (u)	8.4±4.8	8.2±4.6	0.69
	≤4	23(19)	42(20.7)	0.78
	4.1-10	61(50.4)	123(60.6)	0.08

	>10	37(30.6)	37(18.2)	0.01
	Max	24	28	
	Plasma	894±646	876±608	0.80
	< 1000	80(66.1)	140(69)	0.62
	1000-2000	31(25.6)	46(25.6)	>0.99
	>2000	7(5.8)	15(4.4)	0.60
	Max	4040	4600	
PPH management	Intraoperative approaches ^b			
	B-lynch suture	12(21.8)	43(24.9)	0.72
	Artery ligation	10(18.2)	41(23.7)	0.46
	Hysterectomy	2(3.6)	41(23.7)	<0.01
	Packing in CS	14(25.5)	14(8.1)	<0.01
	uterine balloon tamponade	26(21.5)	7(3.4)	<0.01
	Delivery after 2h (%)	10(8.3)	0(0.0)	<0.01
	Transarterial embolization	8(6.6)	19(9.4)	0.42
	Unscheduled return to the OR	22(18.2)	14(6.9)	<0.01
	Unplanned exploratory laparotomy	13(10.7)	12(5.9)	0.13
	Unplanned hysterectomy	4(3.3)	4(2.0)	0.48

^a percentage is based on the account of vaginal deliveries.

^b percentage is based on the account of Cesarean section deliveries.